

“[S]pace is never an abstract surface on which social life is played out, but is socially produced” (Hubbard, 2012). Discuss with reference to gender.

Merriman and Jones (2012, para.2) describe space as “abstract and concrete, produced and producing, imagined and materialized, structured and lived, relational, relative and absolute”. Hubbard (2012) continues that though this is true, ‘space’ cannot be misinterpreted literally to mean location or region for example. Meanwhile, Doreen Massey (2005, p.39) admits the connectedness of space, and the underlying “political implications of practising it differently”. Though they are differed, the definitions each explain how space is defined by its social uses, cannot be recognized as a sign-posted area and is often constrained by its societally designated political agenda. Space is ultimately determined by those who experience it, and one under-represented societal category of people is those individuals who don't identify with the gender binary or have transitioned from one to another. Specifically, spaces like bathrooms which enforce the idea of a gender binary, or government issued IDs containing incorrect gender signifiers and names, even hospitals can misidentify or diagnose important issues. It is important to understand this community and the problems that they face so they may be resolved and become more accepted in space.

Bathrooms are one such place where issues can arise. This is true for gender non-conforming and trans people, but not for others. Termed ‘spatial differentiation’ it is when one person of a particular social category and another of a different one, have opposing experiences of space due to their category (Cloe Crang and Goodwin, 2013). In one instance a gender non-conforming person is refused access to either the female or male restrooms in their office space. Instead, they are forced to use the bathroom on a different, and unfinished, level. They describe the place as having “piles of plaster and wiring, [with] pools of water everywhere” and being “poorly lit and scary” (Styker and Whittle, 2006, p.243). The bathroom experience for this person versus any of their gender conforming coworkers is drastically different, rather worse, and is an example of space defined by socially constructed barriers like the binary of gender. Another similar example is of a transgender student attempting to use the women's restroom and getting backlash from the student body at her attempt to use “their” space, stating they “feared rape” (Styker and Whittle, 2006, p.709). The student body proposed the use of the Dean’s private restroom, which was not allowed, and the issue was not resolved. The Dean and student body leave their societal concepts of sex and gender as a line on the

abstractness of spaces, like public restrooms, which leaves those like this student; unable to fit in, even through self-definition in agreement with the gender binary. Restrooms have developed from passive public spaces, to being policed by vigilant determiners of sex, based on their own varying experiences of sex and gender. The change in such a space is due to the social expectations enforced on it, and allows space to be segregated into those social categories accepted into it, and those which are not.

Spaces outside of bathrooms which require presentation of governmental or official ID due to legal aspects can be extremely hard to change, and therefore often do not reflect a person's actual identity. Requiring a sex change letter of confirmation from a doctor was necessary for change of name and/or sex marker on driver's licenses, passports, birth certificates, or social security records (national insurance in the UK). Not only this, but until recently a gender transition related name change would also require the previous generative organs to have been "totally and irrevocably destroyed" (Styker and Whittle, 2006, p.234). To change a name or sex on legal ID, a letter from a doctor of confirmation including statement of the complete eradication of the previous sex organs was necessary. Compare this to the ease of changing a name for marriage for example, and the societal barriers start piling up against those in the trans and gender non-conforming social category. Legal sex change made its way to English courts in *Corbett v Corbett* when one cis-gendered man, identifying with the gender assigned to him at birth, sought marriage to a transgender woman who had undergone complete sex-reassignment surgery (Styker and Whittle, 2006). The judge ruled against the woman stating that "'sex is determined at birth' by congruence of chromosomal, gonadal and genital factors" (Styker and Whittle, 2006, p.622), thereby setting precedent for similar cases. While that precedent was later overturned, it only further defined legal observation of sex change to be upon total sex-reassignment surgery (Styker and Whittle, 2006), meaning that those who are pre- or non-operative would be unable to receive governmental gender status aligning with their identity. Some transgender women underwent sex reassignment surgeries despite not truly wanting it, for the sole purpose of holding ID with their correct gender identity. One such woman stating that it "reduces 'woman' to a vagina" (Styker and Whittle, 2006, p.661). Though those legalities were nearly 20 years ago, many are still in place, and gender non-conforming people still do not have an alternative option in many countries including the UK. The US gives three gender marker options of 'M, F or X' to allow for intersex and non-conforming individuals to exist in the legal gender spectrum. These social constructions of gender and sex are deeply seeded into unconscious

history. Not unlike judicial precedent, it dictates how to react upon learning of someone surviving outside the supposed gender binary. Whether a reaction of hatred or acceptance, to be correctly identified in an official capacity is a right given effortlessly to cisgendered individuals who still identify with their sex assigned at birth, verses trans and non-conforming people of a very differently treated social category.

Another birth-given right, which gender non-conforming, intersex and trans people do not observe, is efficient use of hospitals. Be it due to a misdiagnosis or prejudiced medical professionals, their care is different to those outside of this social category. One transgender healthcare activist explains that some healthcare workers are “unable to comprehend the complex configurations of transgender bodies and identities [which] often results in poor health care for transgender people” (Stryker and Whittle, 2006, p.601). Not only this, it leaves transgender and intersex people more at-risk for improperly resolved health issues. One intersex individual describes their experience in (Stryker and Whittle, 2006) as being born with “ambiguous genitals” (p.303). Doctors were unsure of their sex until 3 days later they determined the child to be a boy. A year and a half later, the child underwent ‘sex determination’ at a hospital to investigate their ‘true sex’, at which time the child is redeclared a girl and all history of them being a boy is wiped; from birth certificate to moving towns, and even destroying family pictures (Stryker and Whittle, 2006). Stryker and Whittle (2006) continue that when the child grew up as a woman she presented as such and was distraught to learn of the circumstances of her sex, leading to her seeking help from therapists and friends alike until eventually becoming suicidal. She states, “I could not accept that it was just or right or good to treat any person as I had been treated— my sex changed, my genitals cut up, my experience silenced and rendered invisible” (Stryker and Whittle, 2006, p.304). Another doctor upon seeing the surgery scars of a transgender patient remarked that “the patient’s massive scars were probably the result of the surgeon’s unconscious sadism and wish to scar the patient for ‘going against nature’” (Stryker and Whittle, 2006, p.325). Both examples show the permanence of surgery and how a lack of respect for, and knowledge of other peoples’ bodies, like those from different social categories, can directly lead to their unwellness rather than betterment from healthcare. People from other social categories are also treated poorly in medical spaces. One Chinese cis-gender man was “clubbed to death” in a violent hate-crime during job loss in the US (Stryker and Whittle, 2006, 712). Relatedly, a Medic performing emergency medical treatment on a black transgender woman who was in a car crash, was “laughing and telling jokes” about the

woman's lack of female genitalia. Two somewhat similar instances, connected through acts of injustice, perpetuated under society's expectations of treatment of people outside of one's own social groups. Be those groupings related to ethnicity or to gender identity, it puts people, often the minority, into smaller yet categories, which are only further maintained by medical professionals and their corresponding spaces.

Spaces like bathrooms, government legal requirements, and hospitals all uphold the lack of support given to gender non-conforming and trans people, if not strengthen it. The lives and experiences of people of one social category should not solely produce a space, and though it will never be abstract, space should better reflect the variability of society. Those social groups in the minority still experience spaces, and should be given a chance to do so equitably with their social categorical opposites. Though space has many different definitions, it is ultimately defined by those who experience it.

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